

CLINICAL EVALUTION OF PUNARNAVAAMRUTA GUGGUL IN MANAGEMENT OF VATARAKTA W.S.R. GOUT

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ABSTRACT-

The word *Vatarakta* is made up of two words *Vata* and *Rakta*. It caused due to vitiation of *Vata* as well as *Rakta*. The vitiated *Vata* becomes *Aavrutta* with vitiated *Raktadhadu*. *Vridhhi* and obstructed *Vata* inturn vitiates the whole *Rakta* and manifests as *Vatarakta*. It is characterized by severe pain, tenderness, inflammation and burning sensation in the affected Usually it affect people from high socioeconomic class which *Charakacharya* has mentioned as *Adhyavata*. Similarly , *khudda* means joint and small, hence the disease affecting mostly the smaller joints of the body is called as *Khuddavata* ¹. *Vatarakta* mentioned in ayurvedic text has a very closer resemblance to that of gouty arthritis. Gout is an ancient disease described by Hippocrates as well as in classical Ayurveda texts. Historically, it was known as ‘King’s Disease or Rich Man’s Disease’ ².

KEYWORDS – *Vatarakta, Gout, Vatadosh, Raktadhatu, Punarnavaamrita guggul.*

INTRODUCTION-

Ayurveda is most ancient science of life. The peculiarity of the Ayurveda treatment is its potential to cure and prevent the relapse of the disease.

The disease Vatarakta is documented in classical text of Ayurveda. Ayurveda gives guidelines to treat this confidently and increased quality of life of an individual. There are different modalities for management of Vatarakta. Vatarakta is a disease of Raktavahastrotas and is a Madhyamargagata vyadhi. It is a chronic complex metabolic disorder of the musculoskeletal system affecting the joint starting with Parvasandhi especially Padangushta, characterised by burning sensation in the affected joint with pain, stiffness and swelling over joint which involve vitiated Vata-dosha as well as Raktadhatu.

The present life style not only disturbs the healthy diet but Vihar also, Sedentary life style along with Mental Stress and consumption of Non-veg and highly protein diet, excessive intake of alcohol are some of the causing factors which originate acute exacerbation of Vatarakta.

वायुर्विवृद्धोवृद्धेनरक्तेनावारितःपथि॥

कृत्स्नसन्दूषयेद्रक्तं तज्जेयं वातशोणितम्।

खुडं वातबलासाध्यमाठ्यवातंचनामभिः॥ च. चि २९/१०, ११.

Vayu gets aggravated because of self-causing factors. Being obstructed in its course by the vitiated Rakta, the excessively aggravated Vayu vitiates the entire Rakta. The disease thus is called Vata-Rakta. It is also known by the synonyms like Khudavat, Vatbalasak and Aadhyavat³. Vatarakta located in Paani (hands) is caused by upward Dosha and in Paada (feet) is due to downward Dosha.⁴

The Vatarakta can be correlated with Gout in a modern parlance. Pathology, Clinical features are quite similar to Vatarakta. Gout was historically known as the disease of kings or rich man disease. Prevalence rate of Gout in Indian is 0.2- 2.6 %. In general population, though the conventional methods being used have only symptomatic relief, no curative effect is provided along with many adverse effects. Gout is also called metabolic arthritis. Gout is an abnormality of Uric acid metabolism that results in hyperuricemia, deposition of monosodium urate crystal in joints, soft tissue and renal tubules. In this present case study we are going to find effect of Punarnavaamrita Guggulu in vatarakta. Punarnavaamrita Guggulu are described in Chakradatta chikitsa prakaran and possesses properties which help to pacify Tridosha and does Vata and Rakta shaman which provides a better approach of treatment.

Case Report as Follows-

A 57 years old female patient approached the OPD with the chief complaints of:

Left middle finger swelling along with discoloration

Left feet swelling along with burning sensation of bilateral sole.

Left shoulder joint pain along with difficulty in movements.

Generalised weakness

All the above complains were since 3 months

Past History : No H/o HTN/DM/Asthma
 Surgical History : No H/o of any surgery
 Treatment History : Patient did not take any medication till date
 Family History : All family members are healthy and No H/o severe illness

Personal History : **Table 1- showing personal history**

Occupation: Teacher	Mala: 2 times/day, satisfactory	Druk: Avishesh
Addiction : Nil	Jivha:Saam	Aakruti: Madhyam
Nadi:74/min	Shabdha: Spashta	Bala: Madhyam
Mutra:5-6times/day	Sparsha:Anushnasheet	Raktabhara:130/90 mm of Hg

Objective:-

To study the effect of Ayurvedic treatment in the management of *Vatarakta*.

Materials and methods:-

Centre of Study- YAC and hospital.

Simple Random Single Case Study

Material with daily Treatment and Prognosis

Clinical examination of the patient revealed regression of symptoms due to our Ayurvedic management.

Diagnostic Criteria:-

The patients will be diagnosed based on Ayurvedic and modern parameters. Following signs and symptoms were considered for the diagnosis as mentioned in classical texts:-

- 1) Kandu (Ithing)
- 2) Sandhi Shotha (Swelling of joint)
- 3) Sandhi daha (Burning Senasation)
- 4) Sandhitoda (Pricking pain)
- 5) Twaka krushnata (Discoloration of skin)
- 6) Sfurana (twitching)
- 7) Stabdhta (Stiffness)

- Serum uric acid was considered as investigation based diagnostic tool. Serum uric acid >7mg/dl in males and >6mg/dl in females was considered for diagnosis.
- Investigation done report shows- Serum uric acid- 8.7 mg/dl (7/03/2025)

Table 2: - Showing gradation of symptoms according to WHO scoring pattern⁶

Symptoms	Grade0	Grade1	Grade2	Grade3	Grade4
Swelling	No swelling	Slight swelling	Moderate swelling	Severe swelling	
Discoloration	Normal coloration	Near to normal which looks like normal to distant observer	Reddish coloration	Slight reddish black discoloration	Blackish discoloration
Burning Sensation	No burning	Mild burning	Moderate burning	Severe burning	
Pain	No pain	Mild pain	Moderate pain but no difficulty in moving	Slightly difficulty in moving due to pain	Much difficulty

Table 3:- Showing material used in study⁷

Sr.No	Dravya	Dose	Duration	Aupana
1	<i>Punarnavaamrita Guggul</i>	500 mg	2- 0- 2	Lukewarm water after food

Duration of Treatment :- Total 45 days, follow up taken every 15 days and at 45 th day level of serum uric acid calculated for result also assesment done before and after treatment.

OBSERVATION:-

Table 4 : Showing changes in symptoms before and after treatment

Symptoms	Before treatment	After treatment
left middle finger swelling	3	1
Discoloration	2	1
left feet swelling	3	1
Burning sensation in b/l sole	3	0
left shoulder joint pain	2	1

Table 5 : Showing changes in Serum Uric acid levels

Before treatment (7.03.25)	8.7 mg%
After treatment (21.04.25)	6 mg%

Sancharasthana - Sira

Vyakthasthana- Sandhi

Srotas-Raktavaha,Asthivaha,Majjavaha

Srothodushti prakaara - Sanga

Rogamarga - Madhyama

Srothodushti prakaara- Sanga

Rogamarga-Madhyama

Action of Drug (*Punarnavaamrita Guggul*) used in the Management of Vatrakta:-

Dravyas containing in Punarnavaamrita Guggul helps in reducing the vitiation of Pitta Dosha and Rakta Dhatu and also the Vitiation of Vata Dosha, Main component Guggulu is a great Srotoshodhak also , thus helping in early breakdown of Dosha-Dushya Sammurchchhana. Amrita is great immunomodulator which provides immunity. Triphala and Amrita also help by their Rasayan property. Uricosuric effect may be attributed to Dravyas like Danti,Vidang,Amalaki, Hartaki and Twak. Punarnava has diuretic effect.Guduchi,Aamalaki,shunthi and Twak helps in reducing tridosha overall all drugs helps in reducing sign and symptoms.In this way Punarnavaamrita Guggul has all aspect of Pharmaco-therapeutic effect required for the management of Hyperurecemia induced Gout like Anti-inflammatory,Anti-oxidant,Immuno-modulator,Xanthine Oxidase inhibitor, Uricosuric and Diuretic effects. Punarnavaamrita Guggul as a compound formulation contains drugs which have multidirectional effect on Gout.

CONCLUSION:-

By understanding proper *Nidan*, *Lakshana* and *Samprapti* of *Vatarakta* one can very well keep it under the heading of *Vata Vyadhi* and treat it successfully with proper understanding of *Dosha*, *Dushya* and *Vyadhi Awastha*. Vatrakta is Shakha-gat disease which is caused by vitiation of Vata with Rakta dhatu so called Vata and Rakta vikara.Panchkarma procedure like Snehana(*Sneha* overcomes *Rukshatha* by its *Snigdha* property and the *Sanga* is corrected) ⁸,Swedan(*Ushna guna* of *Swedana* does *Srothoshuddi* and *Ama pachana*, so it relieves stiffness) ⁹, and Basti also plays vital role in treatment in chronic cases. Punarnavaamrita Guggul has significant effect on the symptoms of Vatrakta as described in our texts and this study has proved the same with single drug i.e. Punarnavaamrita Guggul orally taken for contineous 45 days and has significant effect on the level of serum uric acid,which is a prominent marker of diagnosis and prognosis of Vatrakta with special reference to Gout.

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